

Artifact: Meaningful Human-in-the-Loop Checking of GenAI Synthesis for Restricted Languages

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Abstract

This artifact accompanies the paper *Meaningful Human-in-the-Loop Checking of GenAI Synthesis for Restricted Languages*. It provides (1) the PICK VS Code extension for regex synthesis with human-

in-the-loop validation, and (2) anonymized user-study data and Docker images that reproduce the study interfaces and statistical analyses reported in the paper.

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1 Scope

The paper makes the following contributions; each is linked to the artifact component that supports it.

1. PICK is functioning software, deployed as a VS Code extension for regexes (paper section 2). appendix B provides the extension itself, installable via a bundled VSIX or GitHub Codespaces, so reviewers can confirm the iterative candidate-generation and scenario-classification workflow described in the paper.
2. Evidence that PICK’s concrete-example-based workflow helps users validate synthesized formal artifacts against their intended meaning (paper section 4). appendix C contains anonymized data from our user studies and reproduces the results reported in the paper.
 - appendix D describes how to reproduce the regex study interface (paper section 4.2).
 - appendix E describes how to reproduce the access-control policy study interface (paper section 4.3).
 - appendix F describes how to reproduce the LTL study interface (paper section 4.4).

2 Content

The artifact archive contains:

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Dagstuhl Artifacts Series, Vol. VOL, Issue ISS, Artifact No. ART NO., pp. ART:1–ART:8

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XX:2 Artifact: Human-in-the-Loop Checking of GenAI Synthesis

- 27 ■ `pick-regex.vsix` — the PICK VS Code extension (appendix B); code artifact.
- 28 ■ `regex-study-ecoop-artifact.tar` — Docker image for the regex study (appendix D); code artifact.
- 29
- 30 ■ `policy-study-ecoop-artifact.tar` — Docker image for the ABAC study (appendix E); code artifact.
- 31
- 32 ■ `policy-control-ecoop-artifact.tar` — Docker image for the ABAC control condition (appendix E); code artifact.
- 33
- 34 ■ `ltl-study-ecoop-artifact.tar` — Docker image for the LTL study (appendix F); code artifact.
- 35
- 36 ■ `data-analysis-ecoop-artifact.tar` — Docker image for study data analysis (appendix C); code artifact.
- 37
- 38 ■ `user-study-raw-data/` — anonymized raw CSV data from all user studies (appendix C); data artifact, CSV format.
- 39
- 40 ■ `qualtrics-regex-control.pdf` — the Qualtrics survey used for the regex *Control* condition (appendix D); data artifact, PDF format.
- 41

42 3 Getting the artifact

43 The artifact endorsed by the Artifact Evaluation Committee is available free of charge on the
44 Dagstuhl Research Online Publication Server (DROPS).

45 In addition, the artifact is also available at: <https://github.com/sidprasad/pick-regex>.

46 4 Tested platforms

47 **Hardware.** No special hardware is required. Any modern laptop or desktop with at least 8 GB
48 RAM and 20 GB free disk space is sufficient.

49 **Software.**

- 50 ■ Either Visual Studio Code ≥ 1.95 with a language-model provider (e.g. GitHub Copilot), or a
51 GitHub account with access to GitHub Codespaces (appendix B).
- 52 ■ Docker (appendix C).
- 53 ■ A web browser (appendix C).

54 **Estimated time.** Setup: approximately 5 minutes. Kick the tires: approximately 15 minutes.

55 5 License

56 The artifact is available under the MIT License.

57 6 MD5 sum of the artifact

58 2f78bb3882dca87bb316662095cfe3c6

59 7 Size of the artifact

60 958 MB

A Getting Started

Unpack the artifact archive:

```
mkdir artifact && tar xzf ecoop-2026-artifact.tar.gz -C artifact
cd artifact
```

A.1 Kick the Tires (15 minutes)

- 1. Install and run the pick regex tool.** Follow the instructions in appendix B (Option A or Option B) to install the VS Code extension. Enter a natural-language prompt (e.g. “*unix filepaths*”) and confirm that candidates are generated and that the upvote/downvote workflow functions as described.
- 2. Reproduce tables and statistics from user study data.** Follow the instructions in appendix C to review the analysis conducted to produce the tables and figures in the paper.

B PICK Regex Tool (VS Code Extension)

This section describes how to access the PICK regex tool shown in paper fig. 2. PICK is a *VS Code extension*, not an LLM or GenAI application per se: it is a developer tool that happens to use a language model in the back end (via the VS Code Language Model API, `vscode.lm`) to generate candidate regexes. The extension is therefore not tied to any particular model or provider—it works with whichever LM provider is available in VS Code (e.g. GitHub Copilot).

We provide two ways to access the tool.

Option A — Local VSIX install. If you are a regular VS Code user and have a language-model provider enabled (e.g. GitHub Copilot), you can install the extension directly:

1. Install the bundled `.vsix` file included in this artifact (see Installing from a VSIX for detailed instructions):

```
code --install-extension pick-regex.vsix
```

Alternatively, the extension is published on the VS Code Marketplace at <https://marketplace.visualstudio.com/items?itemName=SiddharthaPrasad.pick-regex> and can be installed directly from within VS Code by searching for `pick-regex` in the Extensions view.

2. If you do not already have a language-model provider, install the GitHub Copilot extension and sign in with a GitHub account. **GitHub Copilot Free** is included at no cost with any GitHub account and provides access to models (e.g. GPT-4o) with rate limits more than adequate for PICK.

Option B — GitHub Codespaces (zero local setup). If you are not a regular VS Code user, we also provide a running instance via GitHub Codespaces. The repository includes a `.devcontainer` configuration that pre-installs both the PICK extension and GitHub Copilot, so no local toolchain is required. Navigate to <https://codespaces.new/sidprasad/pick-regex> to create a Codespace with everything pre-configured. This option requires a **GitHub account**. GitHub’s free tier provides 120 core-hours/month and 15 GB storage, which is more than sufficient for artifact evaluation; however, usage beyond the free tier may incur cost.

Using the tool. Once the extension is installed (via either option), open the PICK panel in VS Code and ensure a model is selected in the dropdown. Type a natural-language prompt describing the regex you want—for example, you could try “*unix filepaths*”. Because candidates

XX:4 Artifact: Human-in-the-Loop Checking of GenAI Synthesis

101 are generated by a language model, you may not obtain the exact same candidates shown in
102 the paper; however, you can confirm that the tool’s core workflow—upvoting, downvoting, and
103 iteratively refining candidates—functions as described.

104 B.1 Navigating the Regex Extension

105 Regardless of how VS Code is configured, you can always open PICK via the Command Palette:

- 106 1. Open the Command Palette with **Cmd+Shift+P** (macOS) or **Ctrl+Shift+P** (Windows/Linux).
- 107 2. Type View: Show PICK Regex Builder and select the matching command (fig. 1).

■ **Figure 1** Opening PICK from the VS Code Command Palette.

108 This will bring the PICK panel into view. From here, select a language model from the dropdown,
109 enter a natural-language description of the regex you want (e.g. “*unix filepaths*”), and use the
110 upvote/downvote controls to iteratively refine the generated candidates. Verify that the UI and
111 functionality resemble those in paper fig. 2.

112 C Study Data Analysis

113 The `user-study-raw-data/` folder contains the anonymized raw response data from our Prolific
114 user studies:

- 115 ■ `regex-control.csv`, `regex-with.csv`, `regex-without.csv` — participant responses for the
116 three conditions of the regex study (paper section 4.2).
- 117 ■ `policy-control.csv`, `policy-with.csv`, `policy-without.csv` — participant responses for
118 the three conditions of the access-control study (paper section 4.3).
- 119 ■ `ltl-without.csv` — participant responses for the LTL study (paper section 4.4).

120 The data analysis conducted for the user studies in paper section 4 can be reproduced locally with
121 Docker. Load the image from the bundled tar file and run it:

```
122 docker load -i data-analysis-ecoop-artifact.tar  
123 docker run --rm \  
124     data-analysis-ecoop-artifact:latest
```

125 The container runs a single analysis script and prints the computed statistics to standard output.
126 This output should be interpreted as a direct replication check against the corresponding results
127 in the paper. The output is presented in three parts, described below with the expected verbatim
128 output for each.

129 **Regex study accuracy (paper table 2).** The first part reports per-problem accuracies and
130 pairwise chi-squared tests across the three conditions. You should expect the following:

131 Table 2: Accuracy on regex study

132 Problem	Control	With List	Without List	C-v-L	C-v-nL	L-v-nL
133 ----- ----- ----- ----- ----- ----- -----						
134 abWords	22.0%	60.0%	72.0%	13.39, <.001	23.12, <.001	1.11, .2912
135 Times	62.0%	66.0%	84.0%	0.04, .8350	5.07, .0243	3.41, .0647
136 Dates	26.0%	70.0%	66.0%	17.67, <.001	14.53, <.001	0.05, .8303
137 VarNames	50.0%	58.0%	58.0%	0.36, .5472	0.36, .5472	0.00, 1.0000

138 **Regex experience vs. usefulness (paper table 3).** The output also prints a cross-tabulation
 139 of mean accuracy by self-reported regex experience and perceived tool usefulness, corresponding
 140 to paper table 3:

141 Table 3 (Regex Control): Mean accuracy (%) by Regex experience x Tool usefulness

Experience	Very useless	Somewhat useless	Neither ...	I'm not sure	Somewhat useful	Very useful
Never used	-	-	-	25% (n=1)	50% (n=3)	35% (n=5)
Occasional	25% (n=2)	25% (n=1)	42% (n=3)	50% (n=1)	40% (n=10)	40% (n=12)
Regular	-	50% (n=1)	-	-	50% (n=4)	39% (n=7)

147 **Access control study accuracy (paper table 4).** The next part reports per-problem
 148 accuracies and pairwise condition comparisons for the policy study. You should expect the
 149 following, corresponding to paper table 4:

150 Table 4: Accuracy on access control (policy) study

Problem	Control	With List	Without List	C-v-L	C-v-nL	L-v-nL
Accounting	40%	66%	70%	5.78, .0162	7.92, .0049	0.05, .8303
Grading	46%	68%	66%	4.08, .0434	3.29, .0698	0.00, 1.0000
Technology	46%	60%	64%	1.45, .2293	2.59, .1078	0.04, .8368

156 **LTL study (paper section 4.4).** The final part evaluates the LTL claims from paper section 4.4.
 157 First, Fisher's exact tests comparing PICK participants to those in *P23* and *FM24*:

158 RedOnce:
 159 PICK vs P23: Fisher p=0.000, OR=6.27
 160 PICK vs FM24: Fisher p=0.000, OR=6.38
 161 RedOnOff:
 162 PICK vs P23: Fisher p=0.245, OR=1.64
 163 PICK vs FM24: Fisher p=0.830, OR=1.18
 164 RedBlue:
 165 PICK vs P23: Fisher p=0.073, OR=0.47
 166 PICK vs FM24: Fisher p=0.388, OR=0.64

167 Verify that RedOnce shows $p < 0.001$ with $OR \approx 6.3$, matching the paper. Next, non-inferiority
 168 tests (Miettinen–Nurminen score test, 10% margin):

169 RedOnce:
 170 Non-inferiority vs P23: Non-inferior (p=0.000)
 171 Non-inferiority vs FM24: Non-inferior (p=0.000)
 172 RedOnOff:
 173 Non-inferiority vs P23: Non-inferior (p=0.005)
 174 Non-inferiority vs FM24: Inconclusive (p=0.081)
 175 RedBlue:
 176 Non-inferiority vs P23: Inconclusive (p=0.747)
 177 Non-inferiority vs FM24: Inconclusive (p=0.489)

178 Finally, the pooled analysis across all three problems:

179 Pooled (all 3 problems):
 180 PICK: 84/150 = 0.560
 181 P23: 104/240 = 0.433
 182 FM24: 59/134 = 0.440
 183
 184 Pooled NI vs P23: Non-inferior (p=0.000)
 185 Pooled NI vs FM24: Non-inferior (p=0.000)

186 Verify that pooled non-inferiority is confirmed ($p < 0.001$) against both prior studies, matching
 187 the paper's claim.

188 **D** Regex Study Application

189 This section describes how to run the application used for the regex study described in paper
 190 section 4.2. The regex study had three conditions: *Control*, *With List*, and *Without List*. Load
 191 the image from the bundled tar file and start the container. The `SHOW_CANDIDATES` environment
 192 variable controls whether candidates are visible (*With List*) or hidden (*Without List*):

XX:6 Artifact: Human-in-the-Loop Checking of GenAI Synthesis

```
193 docker load -i regex-study-ecoop-artifact.tar
194
195 # With candidate list (withList condition)
196 docker run --rm -p 8080:8080 -e SHOW_CANDIDATES=true \
197     regex-study-ecoop-artifact:latest
198
199 # Without candidate list (woutList condition)
200 docker run --rm -p 8080:8080 -e SHOW_CANDIDATES=false \
201     regex-study-ecoop-artifact:latest
```

202 The application will be available at <http://localhost:8080>.

203 The interaction flow mirrors the regex study procedure described in paper section 4.2.2:

- 204 1. Enter the participant identifier on the Prolific PID page (pre-filled in the artifact build for
205 convenience).
- 206 2. Review and accept the informed consent page.
- 207 3. Complete the screener questions. Select **Yes** for the programming-experience question, then
208 select a regex-experience option indicating at least prior exposure (e.g., seen regexes before,
209 occasional use, or regular use). Selecting **No** or **I'm not familiar with regexes** screens the
210 participant out.
- 211 4. Read the instruction page. Participants are asked to classify examples according to the stated
212 specification, rather than an intuitive interpretation of the description.
- 213 5. Complete the four-part interface walkthrough.
- 214 6. For each regex problem, classify examples until a single candidate remains or all are eliminated;
215 then review and optionally revise classifications before moving to the next problem.
- 216 7. If any classification differs from the expected answer, provide a brief free-text explanation.
- 217 8. Complete the follow-up questionnaire on perceived tool usefulness, confidence, and technical
218 issues.

219 This classify-review workflow repeats for all four regex problems.

220 **Control condition.** For the regex *Control* condition, we include the original Qualtrics survey
221 as `qualtrics-regex-control.pdf` in the artifact root for reference. The survey flow is:

- 222 1. Enter Prolific PID, then the participant must pass the mobile-device check.
- 223 2. Review informed consent and proceed only if consent is granted.
- 224 3. Complete screener questions on programming experience and regex familiarity.
- 225 4. Read task instructions and confirm understanding.
- 226 5. Complete four regex-selection tasks (a/b words, time, date, variable names).
- 227 6. Complete follow-up questions on perceived usefulness and confidence, then return to Prolific.

228 **E** Access-Control Policies Study Application

229 This section describes how to run the applications used for the access-control study described in
230 paper section 4.3. The ABAC study had three conditions: *Control*, *With List*, and *Without List*.
231 The *With List* and *Without List* conditions use the PICK study application, while the *Control*
232 condition uses a separate application.

233 **PICK application (*With List* and *Without List* conditions).** Load the image from the
234 bundled tar file and start the container. The `SHOW_CANDIDATES` environment variable controls
235 whether candidates are visible (*With List*) or hidden (*Without List*):

```
236 docker load -i policy-study-ecoop-artifact.tar
237
238 # With candidate list (withList condition)
239 docker run --rm -p 8080:8080 -e SHOW_CANDIDATES=true \
240     policy-study-ecoop-artifact:latest
241
242 # Without candidate list (woutList condition)
243 docker run --rm -p 8080:8080 -e SHOW_CANDIDATES=false \
244     policy-study-ecoop-artifact:latest
```

245 The application will be available at <http://localhost:8080>.

246 The interaction flow mirrors the access-control study procedure described in paper section 4.3.2:

- 247 1. Enter the participant identifier on the Prolific PID page (pre-filled in the artifact build for
248 convenience).
- 249 2. Review and accept the informed consent page.
- 250 3. Complete the screener questions. Select **Yes** for the programming-experience question, then
251 confirm familiarity with Boolean logic. Selecting **No** for either question screens the participant
252 out.
- 253 4. Read the tutorial page, which introduces access-control policies, explains what subjects, actions,
254 resources, and attributes are, and walks through an example request and its decision (permit
255 or deny).
- 256 5. Complete the training questions (3–4 sample classifications with feedback) to ensure under-
257 standing of the setting.
- 258 6. Complete the interface walkthrough.
- 259 7. For each access-control problem, classify request scenarios until a single candidate policy
260 remains or all are eliminated; then review and optionally revise classifications before moving to
261 the next problem.
- 262 8. If any classification differs from the expected answer, provide a brief free-text explanation.
- 263 9. Complete the follow-up questionnaire on prior access-control experience, perceived tool useful-
264 ness, confidence, and technical issues.

265 This classify-review workflow repeats for all three access-control problems.

266 **Control condition.** Load the image from the bundled tar file and start the container:

```
267 docker load -i policy-control-ecoop-artifact.tar
268 docker run --rm -it -p 8080:8080 \
269     policy-control-ecoop-artifact:latest
```

270 The application will be available at <http://localhost:8080>.

271 The *Control* condition does not use PICK. Instead of classifying scenarios, participants select a
272 policy directly from a static list of candidates. The flow is:

- 273 1. Steps 1–5 are the same as for the PICK application (identifier, consent, screener, tutorial, and
274 training).
- 275 2. For each access-control problem, review the candidate policies and select the one that matches
276 the description, indicate that none is correct, or indicate uncertainty.
- 277 3. Complete the same follow-up questionnaire.

F LTL Study Application

This section describes how to run the application used for the LTL study described in paper section 4.4. Load the image from the bundled tar file and start the container:

```
docker load -i ltl-study-ecoop-artifact.tar
docker run --rm -it -p 8080:8080 \
  ltl-study-ecoop-artifact:latest
```

The application will be available at <http://localhost:8080>.

The interaction flow mirrors the LTL study procedure described in paper section 4.4.2:

1. Enter the participant identifier on the Prolific PID page (pre-filled in the artifact build for convenience).
2. Review and accept the informed consent page.
3. Complete the screener questions. Select **Yes** for the programming-experience question, then confirm familiarity with Boolean logic. Selecting **No** for either question screens the participant out.
4. Read the tutorial page, which introduces the domain—an instrument panel with three colored lights (Red, Green, Blue)—gives an example trace, and explains what it means for a trace to be consistent or inconsistent with a temporal description.
5. Complete the training questions (3–4 sample classifications with feedback) to ensure understanding of the setting.
6. Complete the interface walkthrough.
7. For each LTL problem, classify trace scenarios until a single candidate remains or all are eliminated; then review and optionally revise classifications before moving to the next problem.
8. If any classification differs from the expected answer, provide a brief free-text explanation.
9. Complete the follow-up questionnaire on prior LTL experience, familiarity with temporal-reasoning tools, perceived tool usefulness, confidence, and technical issues.

This classify-review workflow repeats for all three LTL problems. Note that, unlike the regex study, candidates are not shown to participants (without-list condition) to avoid requiring participants to read LTL formulae.

G Reusability

The PICK VS Code extension is open-source and available at:

<https://github.com/sidprasad/pick-regex>

Its architecture is built for reuse and adaptation to other domains, with two main layers:

- **Core algorithm** (`pickController.ts`). Manages the candidate elimination loop: tracking candidates, computing vote thresholds, detecting termination, and requesting distinguishing scenarios. This module is independent of any particular formal language.
- **Domain analyzer** (`regexAnalyzer.ts`). Provides three operations: membership testing, semantic equivalence checking, and distinguishing-scenario generation. The core controller delegates to these operations without knowledge of the underlying language.

As described in paper section 2.3, PICK can be used with any formal language that supports closure under complement and intersection (to compute set differences between candidates) and decidable membership with a generative sampling process (to produce concrete scenarios). To instantiate PICK for a new domain, one replaces the domain analyzer with an implementation that provides the three operations above for the target language.